

LET'S TALK ABOUT **SOLAR ECLIPSES**

Sun	Sol	太阳	Soleil	Gyemk	Jóhonaa'éi
Earth	Tierra	地球	Terre	Ha'lidzox	Nahasdzáán
Moon	Luna	月亮	Lune	Gyemk	Tł'éhonaa'éi
Solar Eclipse	Eclipse Solar	日食	Eclipse Solaire	Awaas gyemga gyiisga ha'lidzoga dił gyemk	Jóhonaa'éi łahgo át'iilyaa
Shadow	Sombra	影子	Ombre	Gano'ots'n	Bichaha'oh
English	Spanish	Chinese	French	Sm'álgyax	Diné

Join us for an annular solar eclipse on Saturday, October 14, 2023, and a total solar eclipse on Monday, April 8, 2024. Find resources to excite and engage learners of all ages at science.nasa.gov/eclipses/resources

Find more multilingual vocabulary to spread the word about eclipses at science.nasa.gov/eclipses/glossary

Sm'álg yax is the language spoken by the Tsimshian People who have lived for thousands of years on the coast of Southeast Alaska and British Columbia, Canada. These terms were translated into Sm'álg yax by Marcella Se'íga Asicksik and provided by the University of Alaska Fairbanks.

Diné bizaad is the language spoken by the Navajo Peoples whose ancestral lands are located primarily in the Southwestern U.S. These terms were translated into Diné by the Indigenous Education Institute.

When watching a partial eclipse, annular eclipse, or partial phases of a total solar eclipse directly with your eyes, you must look through the safe solar viewing glasses ("eclipse glasses") or other safe solar filters at all times. Learn more about eclipse safety at go.nasa.gov/EclipseEyeSafety.

go.nasa.gov/Eclipses

Front Image: Composite image of the partial phases of the total solar eclipse seen in Wyoming on August 17, 2017. Credit: Keon Gibson.

Back Image Credit: NASA/Kristen Perrin

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